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1 Introduction

WP8 deals with the development, organization and implementation of **Transnational Access** of users to the different **RISIS datasets**. It is organized in a systematic and centralized manner (managed by AIT as central access coordinator), aiming to provide all necessary logistical (e.g. offices), technological (e.g. computer environment) and academic supporting (e.g. scientific support, on-the-job training) requirements for RISIS users. Access is organized both conventional (physical) and on distance. Table 1 provides an overview on the different datasets and their coordinating research organizations that have been fully accessible for project-based research from M1 until M18. Note that four new datasets are planned to be opened in the next reporting period (refer to WP10 reporting for further information).

Table 1: Accessible RISIS datasets (M1-M18)

Dataset	Content	Coordinator
Cheetah	Geographical, industry and accounting information on mid-sized firms that experienced fast growth	POLIMI
CIB / Cinnob	Database about largest R&D performers and their subsidiaries, providing patenting and other indicators	UPEM
CWTS Publication	Full copy of Web of Science (WoS) with enhancements e.g. on standardized organization names and other	UL
EUPRO	Systematic and standardized information on R&D projects of different European R&D policy programmes	AIT
JOEP	European trans-national joint R&D programmes, storing a basic set of descriptors on the programmes and agencies	CNR
More	Comprehensive empirical studies on researcher's mobility in Europe	NIFU
Nano	Publications and patents between 1991 and 2011 about Nanoscience and -technology	UPEM
Profile	Longitudinal study on the situation of doctoral candidates and their postdoctoral professional careers at German universities	DZHW
RISIS-ETER	Extension by additional indicators in terms of research activities of the European Tertiary Education Register	USI
RISIS Patent	Enriched and cleaned version of the PATSTAT database on patents, with a standardized name and geolocalization	UPEM
SIPER	Unique database and knowledge source of science and innovation policy evaluations worldwide	Fraunhofer
VICO	Geographical, industry and accounting information on start-ups that received at least one venture capital investment	POLIMI

Notes: Raw data accessible for confirmed project-based research activities (see Section 2)

The objective of this Deliverable is, first, to give an overview on the development and implementation of Access principles, procedures, mechanisms and technical facilities during the first reporting period (see Section 2). Second, it will provide a first monitoring of some substantive and organizational characteristics of the project-based accesses to RISIS datasets during the first reporting period (see Section 3).

Note that further content-wise details and information on the projects that are worked on by RISIS users can be taken from the dataset specific progress reports. Detailed and comprehensive information on the datasets per se (documentation, tutorials, maintenance and deepening of the datasets) are uploaded to the RISIS zenodo space (<https://zenodo.org/communities/risis>) and documented in respective WP deliverables of the first reporting period (**Deliverables D5.1 and D5.2, Deliverable D8.1, Deliverable D9.1**).

2 Access to RISIS datasets via the datasets portal

2.1 Basic access principles

RISIS provides full Access to the datasets listed in Table 1. Under Access we understand the **project-based, scientific usage** (publishable research) of RISIS datasets under the specific RISIS access rules as defined in the RISIS Code of Conduct (<https://rcf.risis2.eu/codeofconduct>). When Access is granted in this way, a user can extract and process raw data in the research project proposed by the user. It is worth noting at this point that at the same time RISIS provides **fully public indicators, datasets and services** (e.g. RISIS-KNOWMAK, OrgReg, FirmReg, Cortext, Gate). These have been developed in RISIS responding to demand from the scientific and policy community, and do not fall under these access criteria. They are open for any researcher or non-research users such as research managers or policy makers (see respective links on the RISIS Core Facility RCF: <https://rcf.risis2.eu>).

In the context of project-based, scientific Access, we basically distinguish between

- ‘Physical’ Access, conducted in form of a physical visit of the user to the location of the dataset of interest (see locations above)
- ‘Virtual’ Access, enabling the user to access RISIS datasets at a distance via online access channels (e.g. via the RCF, other data transmission tools, or even by email)

Access is **free of charge** which implies re-imburement of visiting costs for physical accesses (in case of transnational accesses; intra-national access is possible and also free of charge, but reimbursement of travel is not granted). The **RISIS Code of Conduct** (<https://rcf.risis2.eu/codeofconduct>) sets out the legal and ethical access principles, defining the principle of ‘**Controlled Access**’ that involves user registration and authentication, and an application with a reproducible research purpose (research proposal of about 200 words and a clarification which datasets are needed for the proposed research) that is evaluated by RISIS and an external **Project Review Board** (PRB). RISIS users are supported by the research teams responsible for a specific dataset in terms of data extraction, data handling, etc., both in virtual and physical visits (the latter also including the provision of office environment, etc.).

The modality of access is equally organized across the different datasets, managed and coordinated by the central Access coordinator (see Section 2.3). Technically, Access has been organized via the **RISIS datasets portal**, an online architecture for registration and authentication of users, and the

evaluation and selection of research proposals (see Section 2.4). It also comprises complete documentation, exemplary use cases, and metadata for each infrastructure. Data and results of users' research projects are clearly – as also outlined in the Code of Conduct – subject to **Open Science**, i.e. users must publish data and research outcomes (presentations, papers, etc.) in the RISIS zenodo space (<https://zenodo.org/communities/risis>) and acknowledge RISIS in all related research outcomes.

2.2 The RISIS datasets portal as entry point for access

The RISIS datasets portal constitutes the centralized entry point for Access in the way as described in the previous section (project-based, publishable research). It is an online architecture directly placed in the RCF (<https://rcf.risis2.eu/datasets>) that handles in a consistent manner all **user applications**, **project evaluation** and **selection procedures**.

Figure 1: The RISIS datasets portal front page

Welcome to RISIS Datasets Portal!

Access to RISIS datasets listed below, is free of charge and is offered through a two-step process:

- Accreditation: researchers need to register and agree on the conditions of use (good use of data, authorship, mentions to the RISIS project, agreement of posting results and aggregated datasets produced on RISIS website) via signing the [RISIS Code of Conduct](#).
- Selection: researchers need to propose a project (200 words) based upon the mobilisation of one or more datasets. Projects are reviewed both by the dataset producers and by the RISIS project review board that will give the final agreement for access.

All datasets can be accessed by [Registering](#) or [Login in](#), selecting the needed Dataset(s) then the **Continue Access** option, intending distant access to the selected dataset, or a physical visit to the location of the dataset owner, with costs covered by RISIS ([reimbursement form](#)).

CHEETAH , CIB / CinnoB ▾

Selected datasets:

CHEETAH CIB / CinnoB

[Continue Access](#)

CHEETAH

Cheetah is a database featuring geographical, industry and accounting information on three cohorts of mid-sized firms that experienced fast growth during the periods 2008-2011, 2009-2012 and 2010-2013

[Metadata](#) [Remove from selection](#) [Check Applications](#)

CIB / CinnoB

The CIB / CinnoB - Corporate Invention and Innovation Boards is a database about largest R&D performers and their subsidiaries worldwide, providing patenting and other indicators

[Metadata](#) [Remove from selection](#) [Check Applications](#)

The main intention in the development of the portal has been to keep it as simple as possible for the user, while at the same time ensuring stable and robust handling of incoming proposal, both for the users, the dataset access managers and the PRB (see also Section 2.3). The portal features four main subsections, that is registration, application, evaluation and selection/decision:

- The **registration interface** enables user to register to RISIS, creating a user log-in by providing just very basic user information (name and email address). Most importantly, by registration the user confirms with the RISIS Code of Conduct.
- The **application interface** (as illustrated by Figure 1) enables registered and logged in users to pose a research proposal in the portal in order to get access to one or more RISIS datasets (multiple selection of datasets is possible). After selection of one or more datasets, the user is handed over to an online mask for submission of short proposals, including an academic CV to be uploaded by the user (see Figure 2).

Figure 2: The datasets portal application interface

Access Request for: "CHEETAH,CIB / CinnoB"

Project Title	<input type="text"/>
Project Acronym	<input type="text"/>
Project summary	<input type="text"/>
Project Objectives (200 words) description	<input type="text"/>
Data needed	<input type="text"/>
Choose main dataset	<input type="text"/>
Type of access for CHEETAH	<input type="text" value="Distant"/>
Type of access for CIB / CinnoB	<input type="text" value="Distant"/>
CV (PDF Format)	<input type="button" value="Choose File"/> No file chosen
<input type="button" value="Save"/>	

- After submission of a proposal by the user, the **evaluation interface** comes into play. Both RISIS (represented by the dataset managers) and the external PRB evaluate each proposal against certain criteria, including scientific originality, scientific and policy relevance and clarity of the proposal (see Figure 3). The decision can be negative or positive advice, as well as revise, giving the user the possibility to adapt the research proposal accordingly. In case of positive advice, the user is granted access to the datasets asked for, while in negative advice access cannot be granted (e.g. since data are not usable for the proposed research).

Figure 3: The project evaluation interface

Main Access Manager evaluation		
Is the proposed research new and original?	high	
Is the proposed research scientifically relevant?	high	
Is the proposed research relevant in a policy context?	high	
Is the proposal clear (in terms of scientific objectives and requested data)?	high	
Final Decision	yes	
Reasoning	Very good	
Secondary datasets decisions:		
Dataset	Decision	Reasoning
CHEETAH	Revise	Data needed should be more detailed
NANO	Yes	Good
Final decision of the access request by Main Access Manager		
Advise positive/negative/revise	<input type="radio"/> Yes <input type="radio"/> No <input type="radio"/> Revise	
Reasoning	<input type="text"/>	
<input type="button" value="Submit"/>		

- After a decision has been made, the **communication interface** is at stake, sending automated emails to the user and the dataset access managers and the outcome of the application. The whole stages are stored and can be reproduced in the portal.

While the basic principle of the portal will remain stable over the coming years, it will always be subject to adaptations and minor advancements based on feedback from users or dataset access managers. Note also that with the further development of RCF, especially the datastore, user will in the future be directly handed to an online user space where they can directly extract and process data for which access has been granted.

2.3 Access Management

As described above, Access is intended to be organized in a smooth way for users that ensures all necessary **logistical** (e.g. offices), **technological** (e.g. computer environment) and **supporting** (e.g. scientific support, on-the-job training) requirements. Naturally, this requires stringent organization and immense coordination efforts, both between RISIS and users, but also between dataset owners, the access coordinators. Therefore, it has been decided to opt for a model where Access is managed and coordinated centrally, both in technical and substantive terms, by a central RISIS Access coordinator (AIT) and dataset specific Access managers (coming from the partners coordinating the respective dataset, see Table 1).

Figure 4 sets out the basic elements, i) user, ii) central access management, iii) dataset-specific access management, and interactions of the RISIS access management approach. The central Access coordinator (AIT) interacts with the dataset-specific Access managers on the coordination and dataset specific access principles, and their proper integration in the datasets portal (including metadata, documentation, tutorials, etc.). The central Access coordinator also interacts with the user on all generic (including technical questions to the portal) and administrative matters that appear and is responsible for re-imbursement of travel costs to the user in case of physical visits. Accordingly, the interaction between the user and the dataset-specific access managers can be limited to content-related topics, e.g. support in data handling, data extraction, scientific advice. etc.

Figure 4: RISIS access management

The developed RISIS access management has been received as stable and most adequate solution, both by users and by partners coordinating the datasets. It simplifies the interaction between relevant stakeholders, and is clearly a move forward from de-centralized, and therefore more fragmented access in earlier phases of the project. Table 2 provides an overview on the planned project-based, scientific accesses to RISIS datasets according to the GA, before the section that follows gives an overview on the actual accesses from M1 to M18.

Table 2: Planned Accesses (whole project period)

Dataset	Type*	Coordinator	Units of access offered
Cheetah	Core	POLIMI	40
CinnoB	Core	UPEM	30
CWTS Publication	Core	UL	40
EUPRO	Core	AIT	40
IFRIS-Patstat	Core	UPEM	30
JOREP	Accessible	CNR	10
More	Accessible	NIFU	20
Nano	Accessible	UPEM	10
Profile	Accessible	DZHW	20
RISIS-ETER	Core	USI	30
SIPER	Core	Fraunhofer	20
VICO	Core	POLIMI	40
EFIL**	New	CNR	10
ESID**	New	Strathclyde	30
PHD**	New	DZHW	10
Trademark**	New	Fraunhofer	20
Total			400

Notes: *Core datasets subject to maintenance (WP5) and deepening (WP9)

3 Overview on Accesses in the first reporting period

3.1 Overall figures

In what follows, we initially present some basic information on the project-based scientific access requests to RISIS datasets during the first reporting period (01/2019 – 06/2020). Table 3 provides an overview on these basic figures. RISIS has recorded **102 project-based access requests** in total during the first reporting period of the project until June 2020. In light of the overall goal of 400 units of access until end of project (see Table 2), this is a rather positive pathway, having in mind that accesses are expected to increase when the new datasets will be released (two in 2020, two in 2021), and the RCF enables new functionalities, in particular direct data extraction in a dedicated user space (planned to be released by end of 2020, see WP4 reporting).

Table 3: Overall figures on Access (01/2019 – 06/2020)

Access Requests	Numbers
Total	102
Physical	22 (21.5%)
Distant	80 (78.5%)
Accepted	74 (72.5%)
Rejected	22 (21.5%)
In Review	6 (6.0%)
Single requests	77 (75.5%)
Multiple requests	25 (24.5%)
RISIS internal	18 (17.6%)
RISIS external	84 (82.4%)

Notes: Single requests refer to access requests featuring only one dataset, while multiple requests in contrast are access requests featuring more than one dataset (multiple counting).

About one fifth (22%) of the access requests have been traditional physical visits, i.e. the user gets in face-to-face contact with dataset developers for data extraction, data handling, and often also joint research activities, while the majority (79%) are distant accesses (data transfer most often via email or other file transfer mechanisms). This comes very close to our initial expectation expressed in the GA of 80% distant access requests. It is assumed that the share of distant requests will increase, given new possibilities for distant access to be implemented in RCF. However, it is also shown that there will

always be a fraction of researchers that prefer to interact more intensively with dataset developers, sometimes resulting in joint research activities between users and developers.

Turning to the acceptance rate, about one fifth (22%) of the proposals have been rejected. Main reasons for rejecting incoming proposals had been an insufficient description of how the requested data can support the proposed research, or even a scientifically questionable intended usage of RISIS data by users. A few proposals failed as the proposed projects lacked scientific novelty and originality. Looking at the share of requests to multiple datasets, this has equaled to about one quarter (25%), but with an increasing tendency. This is expected to even increase more since the implementation of the multiple selection possibility in the portal in spring 2020 (before these were handled by separate requests). The majority of access requests (82%) has come from external users, i.e. from researchers not affiliated with any of organizations part of the RISIS consortium. This is a quite high value and demonstrates the value of RISIS for the wider scientific community.

3.2 What do users explore?

Reviewing the project-based access request to RISIS during the first reporting period, one can observe a considerable variety of their thematic orientation. Notably, RISIS datasets have received access requests both by researchers from the scientific peer community in S&T studies, but also from related scientific communities, in particular economics, economic geography or organization research. On the one hand, a number of projects addresses generic and cross-cutting research questions in S&T studies and related fields, among them

- Drivers for and impacts of innovation and knowledge production
- Knowledge and innovation dynamics from a geographical perspective
- Innovation systems research (regional, national, sectoral)
- Firm innovation and its drivers (large firms, start-ups and venture capital, fast growing firms)
- Structures and dynamics of R&D collaboration networks
- Public research organizations and higher education, research careers
- R&D funding and policies.

On the other hand, we can observe an increasingly number of projects that shift attention – usually interwoven with some of the generic research foci – to specific thematic and or technological domains. This is now possible given the new focus of RISIS on the topical assignment of data items using ontologies. Among the fields that have been addressed are

- Energy systems and renewable energy sources
- Pharmaceutical and chemical industry
- Information and Communication Technologies (ICT), digitization
- Bioeconomy, circular economy, green technologies
- Marine biology and oceans research
- Transport, especially aerospace.

3.3 Accesses by dataset

An important element of monitoring access requests is to analyze them by dataset. This is probably the most essential element to monitor attractiveness of datasets, and to take respective actions to adapt and/or re-orientate specific datasets or elements of them. In the first reporting period, we can observe a moderately skewed distribution of access requests across the datasets. The highest number of requests has been received for the VICO dataset dealing with start-ups and venture capital (29), clearly indicating that firm innovation is high on the research agenda. Second most access requests (20) have been received by EUPRO, mainly of projects dealing with R&D collaborations from a network perspective, followed by the other R&D output-oriented datasets RISIS-Patent (15) and CWTS publication (11). RISIS-ETER has also recorded 11 access requests showing the significance of higher education research, followed by Profile (5) on research careers. The other datasets had fewer access requests so far due to different reasons, such as very recent releases or major updates (Cheetah, CIB, More), substantive technical changes (SIPER), or decisions not to maintain (JoREP, Nano).

Figure 6: Access by datasets (01/2019 – 06/2020)

Notes: Nano not displayed (zero access requests yet)

Table 2 as an addition to figure 6 relates the access requests with the planned units of access by dataset as given in the GA. This puts the skewed distribution somewhat into perspective, i.e. we have expected to some extent these differences.

Table 2: Access by datasets (01/2019 – 06/2020)

Dataset	Requests	Distant	Physical	Accepted	Rejected	Planned Access in the GA
VICO	29	25	4	17	11	40
EUPRO	20	14	6	16	3	40
RISIS Patent	15	14	1	10	5	30
RISIS-ETER	11	11	0	10	0	30
CWTS Publication	11	10	1	8	2	40
PROFILE	5	2	3	5	0	20
CHEETAH	4	0	4	4	0	30
CIB / CinnoB	3	1	2	2	1	10
MORE	2	2	0	1	0	10
JOREP 2.0	1	0	1	1	0	40
SIPER	1	1	0	0	0	20
NANO	0	0	0	0	0	20
EFIL*	0	0	0	0	0	10
ESID*	0	0	0	0	0	30
PHD*	0	0	0	0	0	10
Trademark*	0	0	0	0	0	20
Total	102	80	22	74	22	400*

Notes: *new datasets not released yet

3.1 Accesses by country and over time

Turning to the geographical distribution of access requests at the level of countries, we find a concentration on Italy in the first reporting period. This may be, on the one hand, explained by the strong relevance of VICO based in Milan attracting a number of closely located researchers, and, on the other hand, word-of-mouth recommendations that has taken place between Italian researchers recommending RISIS to other users. Below we have a quite random distribution across countries, with large countries (Germany, France) having a significant number of requests, as well as the Netherlands. RISIS received a few requests from non-European countries, including two requests from the US, Canada and China.

Figure 7: Accesses by country (01/2019 – 06/2020)

Finally, we take a look at the distribution of access requests over time (see figure 8, submission date in the datasets portal). Two observations deserve to be mentioned. First, we find an increase of access requests after events or conferences where RISIS has been promoted specifically (e.g. EU-SPRI). Second, we did not observe a decline of access requests during the Covid-19 crisis in 2020. Otherwise, the distribution seems quite uniform.

Figure 8: Accesses by month (01/2019 – 06/2020)

4 Outlook and Summary

This first interim report Access has described the opening and functioning of the RISIS datasets portal as effective entry point for users accessing RISIS datasets by means of dedicated research projects and has provided an overview on the project-based access requests during the first reporting period of the project. RISIS has received in total 101 project-based access requests during that time period and is well on track with regard to the planned 400 units of accesses until the end of the project. It has turned out that users come not only from the core community in S&T studies, but also from related fields. They address a number of original research questions with their projects using RISIS datasets, ranging from firm innovation capabilities, to R&D collaboration networks and innovation and knowledge dynamics at different levels, including regions and countries but also the organizational level. Moreover, they are addressing different technological domains, in particular those seen as critical for future societal development, such as energy, ICT or green technologies.

Over the next months, Access in RISIS will go on and develop further along certain aspects. *First*, the datasets portal will potentially be further adapted and advanced based on user feedback or suggestions from the dataset access managers. While the backbone of the portal is in place and has been received well by the different stakeholders, minor adaptations and improvements are always on the table. As the next major advancement of the portal will be the direct connection to the datastore and an online user space within the RCF platform, where users will be able to directly extract and process data for which access has been granted (see WP4 reporting for details). *Second*, as the most important content-wise step, Access will be gradually extended to the new datasets coming from WP10, starting with trademarks and social innovation (ESID) in 2020, and EFIL and PhD careers in 2021. This will give a push towards new project-based access requests, especially upon integration (actors, geography, topics) of these new datasets with existing ones.

Appendix: List of project-based access requests to RISIS (M1-M18)

Nr.	Project Title	Dataset	Date	Decision
1	Report on the state of research and innovation in Italy	EUPRO	02/2019	accepted
2	Changes in the job composition of the UK labour market and its effect on firm's innovation performance	RISIS Patent	03/2019	rejected
3	European science and technology funding and the direction of the Energy Transition: The case of electricity networks—supergrids or smartgrids?	EUPRO	03/2019	accepted
4	European Aerospace Industry Analysis	EUPRO	03/2019	accepted
5	The perception of radical invention by Venture Capitalists	VICO	03/2019	accepted
6	European Aerospace Industry Analysis	RISIS Patent	03/2019	rejected

7	Leaders and laggards: Typology of regional tertiary education growth in Europe	CWTS Publication	03/2019	rejected
8	Leaders and laggards: Typology of regional tertiary education growth in Europe	RISIS-ETER	03/2019	accepted
9	The effect of tax loss provisions on the venture capital financing of start-ups	VICO	03/2019	accepted
10	The soft budget constraint of VCs - Do startups use investor money efficiently?	VICO	03/2019	accepted
11	European Aerospace Industry Network Analysis	CIB / CinnoB	03/2019	accepted
12	European Aerospace Industry Network Analysis	JOREP 2.0	03/2019	accepted
13	The Government as Venture Capitalist - The influence of German funding programs on the success of young companies	VICO	04/2019	rejected
14	Offshore renewable energy in the Mediterranean Sea	EUPRO	04/2019	rejected
15	EU universities ranking	RISIS-ETER	04/2019	accepted
16	Venture Capital for high-tech firms in Europe	VICO	04/2019	rejected
17	Deal Syndication of VC Investments from the venture-backed companies' perspective	VICO	05/2019	accepted
18	Innovation Data - Comparing bibliometric analysis of raw 'Belgian' bibliometric data from Scopus and Web of Science	CWTS Publication	05/2019	accepted
19	Impact of national economic, political and institutional factors on European Framework Programmes participation	EUPRO	05/2019	accepted
20	PREF PLUS – institutional characteristics of national research systems	RISIS-ETER	05/2019	accepted
21	Internal and external factor effects on SMEs survivability and productivity	VICO	06/2019	rejected
22	Green Industrial Policy: Understanding EU's Regional Low-Carbon Technologies Potential	RISIS Patent	06/2019	accepted
23	Knowledge network dynamics in the presence of shocks: A network-based approach to regional resilience	EUPRO	06/2019	accepted

24	Patterns of bank-affiliated venture capital in Europe - A market overview	VICO	07/2019	accepted
25	Policy for High-Growth innovative enterprises	VICO	07/2019	accepted
26	Innovation dynamics of developed and emerging economies: a comparative study between Europe and Latin America.	EUPRO	07/2019	accepted
27	PhD research on CVC activities	VICO	07/2019	accepted
28	Efficiency analysis of European universities	RISIS-ETER	07/2019	accepted
29	Success strategies of SaaS based Startups	VICO	07/2019	rejected
30	Impact of ICT Technologies on higher education output	CWTS Publication	07/2019	accepted
31	Analysis of the Relationships Between Different Types of Doctorate Programs and Career Outcomes After Graduation	PROFILE	08/2019	accepted
32	Degree Completion and Early Career Outcomes among Science Engineering PhD Students	PROFILE	08/2019	accepted
33	Analysing Doctoral Career Trajectories	PROFILE	09/2019	accepted
34	University characteristics and probabilities for funding of proposals in the European Framework Program	RISIS-ETER	09/2019	accepted
35	Forecasting the Technology Value: Generative Discover by Conditional Variational Autoencoder	RISIS Patent	09/2019	rejected
36	The role of R&D networks in knowledge exploitation and exploration	CWTS Publication	10/2019	accepted
37	The identification of research performed at Aalto University around Social Grand Challenges and Key Enabling Technology: Ontology-driven analysis	EUPRO	10/2019	accepted
38	The identification of research performed at Aalto University around Social Grand Challenges and Key Enabling Technology: Ontology-driven analysis	RISIS Patent	10/2019	accepted
39	Prediction of successful startups	VICO	10/2019	rejected
40	Assessing the role of administrative staff in the (in)efficiency of higher education institutions	CWTS Publication	11/2019	accepted

41	Exploration of changing motivations of PhD candidates in meeting with the labormarket	PROFILE	11/2019	accepted
42	An analysis of knowledge production in Europe	RISIS Patent	11/2019	accepted
43	An analysis of knowledge production in Europe	CWTS Publication	11/2019	accepted
44	An analysis of knowledge production in Europe	EUPRO	11/2019	accepted
45	An analysis of knowledge production in Europe	RISIS-ETER	11/2019	accepted
46	Policy responsiveness of European universities	RISIS-ETER	11/2019	accepted
47	The geography of European Universities collaborations at NUTS2 level: Patents, Publications, and Project Networks	EUPRO	11/2019	accepted
48	The geography of European Universities collaborations at NUTS2 level: Patents, Publications, and Project Networks	CWTS Publication	11/2019	rejected
49	The geography of European Universities collaborations at NUTS2 level: Patents, Publications, and Project Networks	CWTS Publication	12/2019	accepted
50	The growth determinants in Fast growing firms (FGFs)	CHEETAH	12/2019	accepted
51	The geography of European Universities collaborations at NUTS2 level: Patents, Publications, and Project Networks	RISIS Patent	12/2019	accepted
52	The geography of reputation and the role of reputational proximity in multi-scalar R&D networks	EUPRO	12/2019	accepted
53	Participation of Universities of Applied Science in EU Framework Pro-grammes: The research drift as a key driver?	CWTS Publication	12/2019	accepted
54	Participation of Universities of Applied Science in EU Framework Programmes: The research drift as a key driver?	RISIS Patent	12/2019	accepted
55	Quantitative analysis of the ICT impact on higher education	RISIS-ETER	12/2019	accepted
56	How will VC investors influence the level and type of slack resources?	VICO	12/2019	accepted
57	Thesis project on government venture capital funding in the high-tech industry in Europe	VICO	01/2020	rejected

58	Corporate Venture Capital - the 'Blitzkrieg' of the 21th century, running over corporate strategy	VICO	01/2020	accepted
59	Knowledge spillovers in Space	RISIS Patent	01/2020	accepted
60	Innovation management in the space sector	EUPRO	01/2020	accepted
61	Innovation management in the space sector	CIB / CinnoB	01/2020	rejected
62	Innovation management in the space sector	VICO	01/2020	accepted
63	University, innovation and economic growth: a macro and micro analysis	RISIS-ETER	01/2020	accepted
64	High-level BSR value chain mapping exercise	EUPRO	01/2020	accepted
65	Measuring the Effectiveness of Public Venture Capital Funds	VICO	01/2020	rejected
66	Innovation management in the space sector	CIB / CinnoB	01/2020	accepted
67	Relations between Crowdfunding and fast-growing firms	CHEETAH	02/2020	accepted
68	Equity Crowdfunding Deal Structure and the Attraction of Venture Capital Investors	VICO	02/2020	accepted
69	Evidence on how mobility experience affects researcher's career	MORE	02/2020	accepted
70	Determinants and Effects of Cooperation in Homogeneous and Heterogeneous Research Clusters	RISIS Patent	02/2020	accepted
71	The impact of Corporate Venture Capital on innovation of European ventures	VICO	02/2020	rejected
72	How evaluation shapes ocean science. A multi-scale ethnography of fluid knowledge.	EUPRO	02/2020	accepted
73	The geography of interactions between Science and Corporate Technology: A case study on Pharmaceuticals and Chemical sectors	EUPRO	02/2020	accepted
74	Signals in entrepreneurial fundraising	CHEETAH	03/2020	accepted

75	The dynamics of global R&D networks in ICT	RISIS Patent	03/2020	accepted
76	Determinants and Effects of Cooperation in Homogeneous and Heterogeneous Research Clusters	EUPRO	03/2020	accepted
77	Value-creation in Young, Start-Up and Growth Ventures: Syndication of European-based Venture Capital Firms	VICO	03/2020	accepted
78	Crowding-out of PVC: comparison between US and EU	VICO	03/2020	rejected
79	Research on European Venture Capital by its investor types	VICO	03/2020	rejected
80	Entrepreneurial Finance and New ventures	VICO	03/2020	accepted
81	Collaboration in the Circular Economy in the Netherlands; A Proximity Approach	EUPRO	04/2020	accepted
82	Backward patent citations	RISIS Patent	04/2020	rejected
83	Entrepreneurial Career Intentions and University's Entrepreneurial Orientation	RISIS-ETER	04/2020	accepted
84	Dissertation: Knowledge Spillover using a non-linear Spatial Lag Exponential Model	EUPRO	04/2020	rejected
85	Research project "Gender differences along academic careers: achievement of external grants, scientific productivity and career progression"	EUPRO	04/2020	rejected
86	The treatment effect of VC on companies with inventions	VICO	04/2020	accepted
87	The emergence of nanocellulose as a potential breakthrough innovation in the bioeconomy	CWTS Publication	04/2020	accepted
88	The emergence of nanocellulose as a potential breakthrough innovation in the bioeconomy	RISIS Patent	04/2020	accepted
89	Does GVC capital spur innovation in europe in the period 2008-2014	RISIS Patent	04/2020	rejected
90	Does GVC capital spur innovation in europe in the period 2008-2014	VICO	04/2020	rejected
91	Mid-sized fast-growing Italian firms and structural change. An empirical investigation.	CHEETAH	05/2020	accepted

92	Innovative business models for energy and water companies	VICO	05/2020	accepted
93	Drivers of Venture Capital in Europe	VICO	06/2020	accepted
94	PhD research (part of the 'PPR: cultiver et proteger autrement')	RISIS Patent	06/2020	accepted
95	The Effect of Participating in EU Framework Programmes on The International Collaboration Pattern of Turkish Universities	EUPRO	06/2020	in review
96	The Effect of Participating in EU Framework Programmes on The International Collaboration Pattern of Turkish Universities	CWTS Publication	06/2020	in review
97	The Effect of Participating in EU Framework Programmes on The International Collaboration Pattern of Turkish Universities	MORE	06/2020	in review
98	The Effect of Participating in EU Framework Programmes on The International Collaboration Pattern of Turkish Universities	RISIS-ETER	06/2020	in review
99	Cultural distance and Venture Capital investments	VICO	06/2020	accepted
100	Regional variation in the emergence of fast growth firms	CHEETAH	06/2020	accepted
101	Going Global to Stay Local: The Effect of International Syndication Experience on the Performance of Domestic Venture Capital Investments	VICO	06/2020	in review
102	Climate Change Policy Mixes: From Technology to Business Model Innovation	SIPER	06/2020	in review